

ON PEARSONS EMPIRICAL MEDIAN AND THE TRUE MEDIAN

LARSSON A.

ABSTRACT. In this paper we analyze Pearson's empirical relation between the mean, median, and mode, which provides an approximate formula for estimating the median. We formally compare the empirical median with the true median and define the absolute approximation error between them. The behavior of this error is examined to understand the conditions under which the empirical relation agrees with or deviates from the true median.

1. INTRODUCTION

Suppose that n observation are obtained from a data. Denote the values of the n observation to x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , and here x_1 is the first sample observation, x_2 being the second and then so on. Then the mean, which is denoted by \bar{x} , then is given by the whole observation divided by the number of observation.

$$(1) \quad \bar{x} = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

Or to put it this way \bar{x} is the center of the set. Then in the case of grouped data we have the mean of grouped data. The average of a set of data is given by, sum of observation divided by the number of observation. Similar to (1). If, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are the number of observation and f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n are the frequencies respectively.

Therefore,

$$(2) \quad \bar{x} = \frac{(f_1x_1 + f_2x_2 + \dots + f_nx_n)}{(f_1 + f_2 + \dots + f_n)}$$
$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i f_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n f_i}$$

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The media of a set is defined to be the middle value when all value are arranged in ascending and descending order. If the number of values of data is odd the median is the exact middle value however, if the values of data is even the median is said to be the average of the two middle values. The calculation of mode from a set of data is the observation which occur the most.[2]

The empirical relationship between the mean, median, and mode originates from the work of Karl Pearson in his studies on skewness in the late nineteenth century.[3] Pearson proposed the first coefficient skewness

$$(3) \quad Sk_1 = \frac{mean - mode}{SD}$$

Then he proposed the second coefficient skewness

$$(4) \quad Sk_2 = \frac{3(mean - median)}{SD}$$

For moderately skewed unimodal distributions, Pearson suggested they are approximately equal:

$$\frac{mean - mode}{SD} \approx \frac{3(mean - median)}{SD}$$

assuming $SD \neq 0$

$$(5) \quad mean - mode \approx 3(mean - median)$$

Rearranging,

$$(6) \quad -mode \approx 2mean - 3median$$

multiply by both side,

$$-mode \times -1 \approx 2mean - 3median \times -1$$

We have,

$$(7) \quad mode \approx 3median - 2mean$$

From here median will be given by,

$$mode + 2mean \approx 3median$$

Divide both sides by 3 we attain,

$$(8) \quad \text{median} \approx \frac{\text{mode} + 2\text{mean}}{3}$$

It should be emphasized that this relationship is empirical rather than exact; it holds approximately for moderately skewed unimodal distributions and does not constitute a mathematical identity.

2. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE EMPIRICAL AND TRUE MEDIAN

We define the difference of empirical median as $E(X)$ for any set X where set X is defined as, $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subset \mathbb{R}$ where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then we will define the empirical median as $\text{med}_{\text{emp}}(X)$ for any set X , and then we define the true median as $\text{med}(X)$ for any set X . Then we define the whole difference of the two empirical median and true median as:

$$(9) \quad E(X) = |\text{med}(X) - \text{med}_{\text{emp}}(X)|$$

The absolute error is defined as the magnitude of the difference between the true median and the empirical median.

Proposition 1. *Let X_1 be a finite symmetric unimodal dataset centered at c . Then $\bar{x} = \text{med}(X_1) = \text{mo}(X_1) = c$ and consequently, $\text{med}_{\text{emp}}(X_1) = c$. Hence, Pearson's empirical formula yields the exact median.*

Proof. Since X_1 is symmetric about c , for every deviation d from c , the values $(c - d)$ and $(c + d)$ both occur in X_1 with equal frequency.

Each symmetric pair contributes

$$(c - d) + (c + d) = 2c$$

to the total sum.

Suppose there are k such symmetric pairs and that c itself occurs m times. Then the total sum of the observations is

$$2ck + mc,$$

and the total number of observations is

$$n = 2k + m.$$

Thus the mean is

$$\bar{x} = \frac{2ck + mc}{2k + m} = c.$$

By symmetry, exactly half of the observations lie below c and half lie above c , so the median is

$$\text{med}(X_1) = c.$$

Since X_1 is unimodal with unique mode at c , we also have

$$\text{mo}(X_1) = c.$$

Substituting into Pearson's empirical formula,

$$\text{med}_{emp}(X_1) = \frac{\text{mo}(X_1) + 2\bar{x}}{3} = \frac{c + 2c}{3} = c.$$

Therefore, under symmetry, the empirical median equals the true median. \square

Proposition 2. *Let $X_n = \{a, a, \dots, a, b, n\}$ be a dataset in which a appears $k \geq 2$ times, b is fixed, $n \in \mathbb{R}$ and where $n > b \geq a$. Assume that the median and the mode of X_n are equal to a .*

Then, as $n \rightarrow \infty$, the error

$$E(X_n) = |\text{med}(X_n) - \text{med}_{emp}(X_n)|$$

Then,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E(X_n) = \infty$$

Proof. Since a appears $k \geq 2$ times and n is a single value, the ordering of the dataset does not affect the central position for sufficiently large n . Hence,

$$\text{med}(X_n) = a.$$

Because a occurs most frequently, we also have

$$\text{mo}(X_n) = a.$$

The mean of the dataset is

$$\bar{x} = \frac{ka + b + n}{k + 2}.$$

Using Pearson's empirical formula,

$$\text{med}_{emp}(X_n) = \frac{\text{mo}(X_n) + 2\bar{x}}{3} = \frac{a + 2\left(\frac{ka+b+n}{k+2}\right)}{3}.$$

Simplifying,

$$\text{med}_{emp}(X_n) = \frac{a(k+2) + 2(ka+b+n)}{3(k+2)}.$$

Expanding,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{ak + 2a + 2ka + 2b + 2n}{3(k+2)} \\ &= \frac{3ka + 2a + 2b + 2n}{3(k+2)}. \end{aligned}$$

Observe that the only term depending on n is $\frac{2n}{3(k+2)}$, which grows linearly as n increases.

Since the true median remains equal to a , the absolute error is

$$E(X_n) = \left| a - \frac{3ka + 2a + 2b + 2n}{3(k+2)} \right|.$$

As $n \rightarrow \infty$, the term $\frac{2n}{3(k+2)}$ increases without bound, while all other terms remain constant.

Therefore,

$$E(X_n) \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence, the empirical approximation fails in the presence of a sufficiently large outlier. \square

Proposition 3. *Let, $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subset \mathbb{R}$ where, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ for any constant $c \in \mathbb{R}$ we define the translated dataset as $X + c := \{x_1 + c, \dots, x_n + c\}$ then the error is translation invariant. $E(X + c) = E(X)$, $\forall c \in \mathbb{R}$*

Proof. Adding a constant c to every observation increases the mean, median, and mode each by c . That is,

Adding c to every elements,

$$X + C = \{x_1 + c, x_2 + c, \dots, x_n + c\}$$

$$X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$$

For mean,

$$\bar{x} = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

and we also have,

$$\bar{x}_{X+c} = \frac{(x_1 + c) + (x_2 + c) + \dots + (x_n + c)}{n}$$

grouping terms,

$$\bar{x}_{X+c} = \frac{x_1 + \dots + x_n + nc}{n} = \frac{x_1 + \dots + x_n}{n} + \frac{nc}{n} = \frac{x_1 + \dots + x_n}{n} + c$$

$$(10) \quad \bar{x}_{X+c} = \bar{x} + c$$

Now, for median, if,

$$x_1 \leq x_2 \leq x_n$$

then,

$$x_1 + c \leq x_2 + c \leq x_n + c$$

So,

$$(11) \quad \text{med}(X + c) = \text{med}(X) + c$$

for mode, the addition of constant c to every element will not change the frequency of the elements.

$$(12) \quad mo(X + c) = mo(X) + C$$

inserting (!0), (11) and (12) in the empirical median formula,

$$med_{emp}(X + c) = \frac{mo(X + c) + 2\bar{x}_{X+c}}{3}$$

$$med_{emp}(X+c) = \frac{mo(X) + c + 2(\bar{x} + c)}{3} = \frac{mo(X) + 2\bar{x} + 3c}{3} = \frac{mo(X) + 2\bar{x}}{3} + \frac{3c}{3}$$

$$(13) \quad med_{emp}(X + c) = med_{emp}(X) + c$$

now using (12) and (13) in Error Approximation formula,

$$E(X+c) = |med(X+c) - med_{emp}(X+c)| = |med(X) + c - (med_{emp}(X) + c)|$$

Therefore,

$$(14) \quad E(X + c) = E(X)$$

□

Proposition 4. *Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ be a finite dataset and let $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$. Define the scaled dataset $\lambda X = \{\lambda x_1, \lambda x_2, \dots, \lambda x_n\}$. Then, $E(\lambda X) = |\lambda|E(X)$.*

Proof. Let us first define the set,

$$X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$$

Then we multiply each elements of the set by λ which yields,

$$\lambda X = \{\lambda x_1, \lambda x_2, \dots, \lambda x_n\}$$

First, finding mean that will be,

$$\bar{x}_{\lambda X} = \frac{\lambda x_1 + \lambda x_2 + \dots + \lambda x_n}{n}$$

Taking common,

$$= \frac{\lambda(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n)}{n}$$

Since, λ is a constant,

$$= \lambda \frac{x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n}{n}$$

That yields,

$$= \lambda \bar{x}$$

Therefore,

$$(15) \quad \bar{x}_{\lambda X} = \lambda \bar{x}$$

Now for mode, in set X with λ multiplied to each elements, λ does not change the frequency of the set therefore,

$$(16) \quad mo(\lambda X) = \lambda mo(X)$$

As for median, If we multiply every value by the same constant, it does not change what is in the middle.

$$(17) \quad med(\lambda X) = \lambda med(X)$$

Now inserting (15), (16) and (17) to empirical median formula,

$$\begin{aligned} med_{emp}(\lambda X) &= \frac{\lambda mo(X) + 2\lambda \bar{x}}{3} \\ &= \lambda \left(\frac{mo(X) + 2\bar{x}}{3} \right) \\ &= \lambda med_{emp}(X) \end{aligned}$$

Now let us find the error approximation,

$$\begin{aligned} E(\lambda X) &= |\lambda med(X) - \lambda med_{emp}(X)| \\ &= |\lambda| |med(X) - med_{emp}(X)| \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$(18) \quad E(\lambda X) = |\lambda| E(X)$$

□

3. AFFINE TRANSFORMATION LAW OF THE EMPIRICAL MEDIAN ERROR

Theorem 1. *Let, $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\} \subset \mathbb{R}$ and let $(\lambda, c) \in \mathbb{R}, \lambda \neq 0$ Then we define the affine transformation, $Y = \lambda X + c = \{\lambda x_1 + c, \lambda x_2 + c, \dots, \lambda x_n + c\}, n \in \mathbb{N}$ Then it satisfies, $E(Y) = |\lambda| E(X)$*

Proof. First finding mean,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{x}_Y &= \frac{(\lambda x_1 + c) + \dots + (\lambda x_n + c)}{n} \\ &= \frac{\lambda(x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n) + cn}{n} \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{\lambda(x_1 + \dots + x_n)}{n} + \frac{cn}{n} = \lambda\bar{x}_X + c$$

Therefore,

$$(19) \quad \bar{x}_Y = \lambda\bar{x}_X + c$$

As for the median of the set, since the value of the middle value is determined by the middle point value, and the transformation $x \mapsto \lambda x + c$ is applied to every single element with the change of the positioning thereby yielding that the median is

$$(20) \quad \lambda med(X) + c$$

Since the mode is defined to be the highest frequency of the set, the high value when $x \mapsto \lambda x + c$ is applied will still preserve the frequency of each observation. thereby yielding the mode is,

$$(21) \quad \lambda mo(X) + c$$

Now inserting (19), (20), and (21) in the median empirical formula,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{\lambda mo(X) + c + 2\lambda\bar{x} + 2c}{3} = \frac{\lambda mo(X) + 2\lambda\bar{x} + 3c}{3} \\ &= \frac{\lambda(mo(X) + 2\bar{x}) + 3c}{3} = \frac{\lambda(mo(X) + 2\bar{x})}{3} + \frac{3c}{3} \end{aligned}$$

$$(22) \quad \frac{\lambda mo(X) + 2\bar{x}}{3} + c = \lambda med_{emp}(X) + c$$

Now inserting the two medians in the error approximation formula,

$$E(Y) = |\lambda med(X) + c - (\lambda med_{emp}(X) + c)| = |\lambda| med(X) - med_{emp}(X)$$

$$(23) \quad E(Y) = |\lambda| E(X)$$

□

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper we analyzed Pearson's empirical median and compared it with the true median through explicit constructions. It was shown that for symmetric unimodal datasets the empirical formula gives the exact value, but this agreement does not hold in general. In particular, the presence of sufficiently large outliers can cause the approximation error to grow without bound. We also proved that the error remains unchanged under translation and scales proportionally under dilation, yielding an affine transformation

law. These results clarify that Pearson's relation is only an approximation and its accuracy depends strongly on the structure of the dataset. Therefore, caution must be taken when applying the empirical median outside moderately skewed distributions.

REFERENCES

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